

Dye-Alcohol Interaction in Aprotic Media

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In the present investigation the carbinol base of ethyl violet has been made to react with various alcohols in aprotic solvents to produce the violet coloured salt. The experimental results fit a formula of the type $K = \frac{(\text{Salt})}{(\text{carbinol base})(\text{Alcohol})^n}$ where n is greater than unity. The behaviour can be fairly satisfactorily explained by considering inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding of alcohol molecules. For 2,2-dinitropropanol the value of n is unity, showing that this alcohol largely exists as monomeric species. The mean heat of reaction for the interaction between 2,2-dinitropropanol and carbinol base of ethyl violet in benzene medium is found to be 6.72 Kcal./mole. The values of the association constant (K) measure roughly the relative acidic strengths of alcohols in aprotic media and it is found that inductive effect plays a dominant role in causing increased acidity of substituted alcohols.

Since benzene and other aprotic solvents are very feebly basic and ionogenic compared to water for determination of relative strengths of acids or alcohols in such solvents, one must compare their interaction against a reference base. Few systematic investigations on such acid-base reactions in aprotic solvents mostly involving acid dyes have been reported¹⁻⁷; these deal mainly with organic acids but little information is available with alcohols. The reasons why hydrocarbons have received little attention in this type of work is mainly ascribable to the fact that most of the cationic dyes are insoluble or very sparingly soluble in benzene. This difficulty can be easily got over by converting the dye into its basic form and extracting it in benzene—a technique first introduced by Palit⁸⁻⁹. This has made it possible to study donor-acceptor type interactions involving dyes in benzene¹⁰⁻¹⁴ and we have utilised the above method in the present investigation with respect to ethyl violet.

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Ordinary alcohols have faintly acidic properties and alcohols substituted with highly electronegative groups behave as acids and sometimes their acidity is comparable to phenol and carboxylic acids¹⁵⁻²³. This acid-like behaviour of some substituted alcohols has been utilised in the present work to study the interaction between several alcohols and the dye-base of ethyl violet in aprotic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Alcohols: Dichlorohydrin (or 1,3 dichloro 2-propanol) was kindly supplied by the B.D.H. Ltd. It was distilled before use. 2, 2 dinitropropanol was obtained as gift from Dr. H. E. Ungnade of Los Alamos Scientific Laboratory. Hexafluoroacetone hydrate was obtained as gift from Dr. W. J. Middleton of E.I. Du Pont de Nemours and Co. Tri-fluoroethanol was kindly supplied by Pennsalt Chemicals Corporation. Fluoroalcohols having the general formula $H(CF_2-CF_2)_nCH_2OH$ (where $n=1$ for C_3 -fluoro alcohol, 2 for C_5 -fluoroalcohol, 3 for C_7 -fluoroalcohol, 4 for C_9 -fluoroalcohol, 5 for C_{11} -fluoroalcohol), were obtained as gift samples from E. I. Du Pont de Nemours and Co. All these compounds were obtained in highly purified form and used as such. Our thanks are due to donors of these chemicals.

Purification of Solvents: The solvents (benzene, toluene, xylene) were purified by standard methods and stored over sodium wire.

Preparation and Isolation of Dye-base: The dye (ethyl violet) was supplied by Allied Chemical Corporation (National Aniline Division). The dye-base was extracted by applying Freeze-drying technique¹¹. About 30-40 mg. of the dye was taken and dissolved in about 50 ml water. Strong NaOH solution (≈ 4 N) was added dropwise to the dye solution until the dye-base was precipitated. About 100 ml of benzene was added to this alkaline mixture and the whole was shaken thoroughly, when the dye-base passed into the upper benzene layer. The benzene extract of the dye was separated by a separating funnel and then frozen in a cooled bath. Benzene was removed from the frozen mixture by applying a rotating vacuum system and the dye-base was obtained as a powder.

The infrared spectra and other studies have shown that the dyebase of ethyl violet is the carbinol base of dye and has the following structure¹²:

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The colourless carbinol base of ethyl violet in aprotic media slowly reacts with alcohols to produce a coloured salt. The extent of formation of coloured salt with various alcohols was measured by spectrophotometric means. The solutions of alcohols and dye-base were prepared gravimetrically and all the spectral measurements were recorded from a Hilger UV speck spectrophotometer using 1 cm. stoppered silica cells, whose temperature was maintained constant within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ by circulating water through the cell holder by a special device. Fig. 1 is the spectra of the violet coloured salt, showing that λ_{\max} is at $605 \text{ m}\mu$. All spectral measurements were taken at this wavelength.

FIG. 1

Fig.1. Spectra of the violet coloured salt in benzene at 25° . Colour developed by : I, Hexafluoroacetone hydrate ($7.945 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$); II, Trifluoroethanol (0.502M). Concentration of carbinol base in both cases is $5.721 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$.

The indicator ratio $(\text{DH}^+\text{X}^-)/(\text{D})$ where XH is an alcohol, D is the carbinol base and DH^+X^- is the coloured salt was calculated from the relation $x_e/(b-x_e)$, where b is the total concentration of carbinol base in terms of optical density (O.D.) and x_e is equilibrium

FIG. 2

Fig.2. Plot of absorbance at different carbinol base concentrations after complete conversion to the coloured form.

concentration of the coloured salt in terms of the same unit. The total concentration of carbinol base in terms of O. D. can be determined by adding excess C_3 -fluoroalcohol to the carbinol base so that further addition of alcohol does not bring about any change in colour and hence in optical density. Fig. 2 shows the plot of absorbance at different carbinol base concentrations after complete conversion to the coloured form as above, and it is found that Beer's law is obeyed by the coloured form in our working range of carbinol base concentration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reaction between carbinol base of ethyl violet and alcohols in aprotic media can be represented as follows:

Since this reaction fails to occur when the alcohol (R-O-H) is replaced by an ether (R-O-R') it is very likely that the hydroxylic hydrogen of alcohol is responsible for the colour change. It is well known²⁴ that the carbinol base of triphenylmethane dyes reacts slowly with acids with the loss of a water molecule to give the ion of the dye which has the structure

where the quinonoid structure and positive charge can be associated with any of the three benzene rings. This ion reacts with hydroxyl ions to reform the carbinol base. Thus it has been shown in this laboratory¹³ that the carbinol base of crystal violet reacts with organic acids and phenol in benzene medium to give the coloured salt where the oppositely charged ions are held together as ion pair and water molecule is possibly associated with any of the species present in this system through hydrogen bond and they exist as one entity. Since our system exhibits similar characteristics, the equilibrium for the interaction between alcohols and dye-base can be represented as

where D is the dye-base and XH stands for alcohol. The association constant is given by

$$K = \frac{(DH^+X^-)}{(D)(XH)} \quad (2)$$

Our experimental results show the following features:

(i) Equation (2) is obeyed within experimental error at a particular alcohol concentration (Table I) i.e. the values of K are constant, when the carbinol base concentration is varied at fixed alcohol concentration.

TABLE I

Values of $(DH^+X^-)/(D)$ at fixed alcohol concentration and different carbinol base concentrations.

(Results with C₅-fluoroalcohol in benzene at 35°)

Concentration of carbinol base $\times 10^6$ M	$(DH^+X^-)/(D)$
4.767	1.11
5.721	1.20
6.674	1.20
7.628	1.16

(ii) However, when the alcohol concentration is varied, the equation (2) no longer holds good, and the value of K increases rapidly with increase in alcohol concentration. This is clearly indicated by the fact that we do not get linear graphs with unit slopes when $\log (DH^+X^-)/(D)$ is plotted against $-\log (XH)$ for different alcohols (Fig. 3). However, for 2, 2 dinitropropanol the slope of such plot is unity, that is equation (2) is obeyed by 2, 2 dinitropropanol (Table II).

TABLE II

Relative strengths of fluoroalcohols, fluoroketone hydrate and some other alcohols in aprotic solvents—as judged from $\log K$ values.

Alcohol	pK_a in water	Benzene		Toluene		Xylene	
		n	$\log K$	n	$\log K$	n	$\log K$
Trifluoro ethanol	11.31	3.8	1.767	—	—	—	—
C ₃ -fluoro- alcohol	11.33	1.80	1.278	1.52	1.034	1.40	0.9239
C ₅ -fluoro alcohol	11.34	2.0	2.62	1.50	2.130	—	—
C ₇ -fluoro- alcohol	11.33	1.58	2.433	1.48	2.354	1.35	2.092
C ₉ -fluoro alcohol	—	1.24	2.641	1.48	2.294	—	—
C ₁₁ -fluoro alcohol	—	1.40	2.758	—	—	1.58	2.922
2,2 dinitro- propanol	—	1.0	2.00	1.0	2.02	—	—
Dichloro hydrin	—	1.62	1.685	—	—	1.50	1.695
Hexafluoro acetone hydrate	6.58	1.60	6.80	—	—	—	—

(iii) For the other alcohols, the experimental results fit well with an empirical formula of the type

$$K = \frac{(DH^+X^-)}{(D)(XH)^n} \quad (3)$$

where the value of 'n' varies from alcohol to alcohol. Similar expressions have been used by Lamer and Downes¹ as well as by Looy and Hammett²⁵ in their investigations on dye-acid interaction in aprotic and other nonaqueous solvents. More recently it has been found in this laboratory¹³ that the results of interaction between carbinol base of crystal violet and several carboxylic acids are expressible by equation (3).

Equation (3) can be written as

$$\log \frac{(\text{DH}^+\text{X}^-)}{(\text{D})} - n \log (\text{XH}) = \log K \quad (4)$$

At 50% salt conversion, the value of $\frac{(\text{DH}^+\text{X}^-)}{(\text{D})} = 1$

$$\therefore \log K = -n \log (\text{XH}) \quad (5)$$

Hence according to equation (4), when $\log \frac{(\text{DH}^+\text{X}^-)}{(\text{D})}$ is plotted against $-\log (\text{XH})$ it

should give a straight line with slope equal to 'n'; such plots are shown in Fig. 3. The curves indicate that good straight lines are obtained for all the alcohols, and except for 2, 2 dinitropropanol where $n=1$, the values of 'n' in all cases are greater than unity. Values of log K for different alcohols can be obtained by applying equation (5).

FIG. 3

Fig. 3. Typical plots of $\log (\text{DH}^+\text{X}^-)/(\text{D})$ vs. $-\log (\text{XH})$. Solvents are indicated in the parentheses :1, Trifluoroethanol (Benzene); 2, C_3 -fluoroalcohol (Benzene); 3, Dichlorohydrin (Benzene); 4, C_5 -fluoroalcohol (Benzene); 5, C_7 -fluoroalcohol (Benzene); 6, 2, 2-dinitropropanol (Toluene); 7, C_{11} -fluoroalcohol (Xylene).

Kolthoff and Bruckenstein²⁶ made somewhat similar observation while studying dye-acid interaction in acetic acid medium. They explained it by considering the partial dissociation of ion-pair IH^+X^- . But this idea of partial dissociation of the salt or ion-pair in acetic acid medium seems inapplicable in these aprotic solvents of very low dielectric constant⁴. Moreover self association of IH^+X^- or dye molecules is negligible in the concentration range we worked^{4,27}.

Our results can be fairly satisfactorily explained by considering intra- and inter-molecular hydrogen bonding of alcohol molecules. Although the hydrogen bonding

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properties of simple alcohols are being studied in details²⁸⁻²⁹, little information so far is available for these large fluoroalcohol molecules. The following are the different possibilities: (i) In the case of trifluoroethanol intermolecular association leading to the formation of dimer and polymers is important³⁰. But still it is claimed that there is considerable proportion of monomeric species³¹. (ii) For C₃-fluoroalcohol both inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding may take place, but for the higher members (that is, C₅-to C₁₁-fluoroalcohols) intramolecular hydrogen bonding leading to the formation of 5-membered or 6-membered ring compounds becomes more important¹⁷. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding sometimes enhances the acidity of proton donor by putting the electron density away from the carboxyl hydrogen atom and easing its departure (as for example, in salicylic acid³²). Moreover, hydrogen bonding in the case of fluoroalcohols may be of the type O-H . . . F or H-O . . . H, depending on the steric factors¹⁷. (iii) It is still a debatable question whether the structure of alcohol dimer is open or cyclic and whether the alcohol trimers and higher polymers are stronger than monomers or dimers³³⁻³⁴. (iv) The extreme acidity of some organic acids has been explained by the fact that carboxylic acids exist to a considerable degree as carboxylic-carboxylate ion complex in inert solvents^{13,35-39}. Similarly phenol exists as phenol-phenolate ion complex^{13,40}. Thus it is not unlikely that alcohols, specially the stronger ones, may exist as alcohol-anion (alcoholate) type complexes.

Combination of all these factors complicates the whole system and will affect the value of 'n'. Thus in the system the alcohol may exist as free monomer alcohol molecules, dimeric (cyclic or open) alcohol molecules, higher associated forms, intramolecularly bonded forms and alcohol-anion(alcoholate) type complexes. The presence of these associated forms accounts for the non-integral value of 'n' which is always greater than unity. Similar explanation has been put forward to account for the non-integral value of 'n' in the interaction of carbinol base of crystal violet and carboxylic acids in benzene medium¹³.

CONCLUSIONS

As shown in Table II the values of log K can be taken as a measure of the strength of various alcohols in aprotic media. Thus we arrive at the following conclusions from our results:

(i) Relative order of strengths of alcohols is same in the three solvents studied (ie. benzene, toluene and xylene).

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(ii) Trifluoroethanol in aprotic media probably exists in highly associated forms leading thereby to large value of 'n' and log K value shows that these associated forms contribute little to the acidity of the alcohol. While studying interaction between carbinol base of crystal violet and phenol in benzene medium¹³, it was found that due to highly associated forms phenol had also large value of 'n', but the existence of the strong phenol-phenolate ion complex in non-aqueous media⁴⁰ sharply increases the acidity of phenol.

C₃-fluoroalcohol probably exists in both intra and inter-molecularly bonded forms and in aprotic solvents its strength is comparable to trifluoroethanol.

(iii) C₅-, C₇-, C₉- and C₁₁-fluoroalcohols are more or less equally auto-complexed and of equal strength. The small difference in the values of K for the individual members of this series is not considered to be much significant.

(iv) Isopropanol ($\text{CH}_2\text{-CHOH-CH}_2$) is too weak to produce any detectable colour change with the carbinol base, but introduction of two chlorine atoms at the two ends increases its acidity sharply and in aprotic solvents dichlorohydrin ($\text{CH}_2\text{-CHOH-CH}_2$) is a strong acid. These facts can be explained by inductive effect. Although hydrogen bonding properties of dichlorohydrin have not been studied, our results suggest that this secondary alcohol exists in various hydrogen bonded forms in aprotic solvents, somewhat like the fluoroalcohol molecules.

(v) In aprotic media hexafluoroacetone hydrate is several hundred times stronger than the fluoroalcohols. The extreme acidity of fluoroketone hydrates has been observed also in aqueous medium and it has been explained by both inductive effect and strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding²².

(vi) The value of 'n' for 2, 2 dinitropropanol is unity, showing that association of alcohol molecules is negligible and it exists as monomeric species. Our results support Ungnade's work on the IR study of 2,2 dinitropropanol⁴¹. Actually the IR absorption spectra of 2,2 dinitropropanol shows predominantly monomeric hydroxyl absorption and single NO₂ stretching bonds, indicative of non-bonded species. While dinitropropanol behaves as a strong acid towards carbinol base in aprotic media the unsubstituted alcohol (i.e., n-propanol) reacts only to a small extent with the carbinol base and behaves as an extremely weak acid. It appears from our results that inductive effect causes a sharp increase in the acidity of 2, 2 dinitropropanol and in aprotic solvents it is comparable to fluoroalcohols.

(vii) Comparison of log K values in aprotic solvents with available pKa's in water as given in Table II shows that the relative strengths of different alcohols, measured in aprotic solvents with reference to carbinol base of ethyl violet change sometimes abnormally when compared with their order in water. However some of the reported pKa values in water may not be quite reliable²³.

Effect of Temperature: Since 'n' is equal to one for 2, 2 dinitropropanol (i.e., the simple mass law equation (2) is obeyed by this alcohol), we took measurements at two

TABLE III

Results with 2, 2 dinitropropanol at two different temperatures. (Solvent : Benzene)

Temp. °C	log K	$-\Delta H$ Kcal./mole
35	2.00	
45	1.85	6.72

different temperatures for this particular alcohol. The results are shown in Table III. The mean heat of reaction calculated from the equilibrium constants at two different temperatures is found to be 6.72 Kcal./mole. Only a few investigations on thermodynamic properties of proton transfer reactions in aprotic solvents with acids as the proton donors have been reported^{5,7,27} and no data involving alcohols have been published yet. The $-\Delta H$ values for most dye-acid interactions reported so far in benzene medium lie between 10-15 Kcal./mole—a value considerably higher than that obtained by us for dye-alcohol interaction.

The authors are grateful to Prof. R. N. Haszeldine of Manchester College of Science and Technology for his help in obtaining various gift chemicals. Thanks are also due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (India) and National Bureau of Standards (U.S.A.) for financial assistance.

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Received, July 7, 1967.